

EVALUATION OF EARLY VASCULAR LESION OF THE RENAL IN DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY

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Introduction: In diabetic nephropathy, pathological changes in the renal vessels occur due to chronically high blood sugar levels, which leads to thickening of the capillaries, narrowing of their lumen, and deterioration of blood flow in the kidneys [1,3]. The filtering element of the kidneys are the renal glomeruli. They are, first of all, damaged by diabetes due to high blood sugar levels. These pathological changes in the renal vessels and glomeruli lead to diabetic nephropathy [2,6]. This destroys the glomeruli - the filtering structures of the kidneys, causing glomerulosclerosis, decreased filtration function of the kidneys, and the development of chronic renal failure (CRF) [4,5].

The aim of the study was to study the features of intrarenal hemodynamics in patients with type 2 diabetes with diabetic nephropathy.

Material and methods. The study included 60 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic nephropathy. Of these, 34 were men and 26 were women, aged 38 to 63 years. The average duration of diabetes was 10.3 ± 0.6 years. According to the classification of diabetic nephropathy (Mogensen SE et al. 1983), the number of patients with normoalbuminuria in the study was 20, with microalbuminuria - 20, and with microalbuminuria and normally elevated blood pressure (140/90-150/100 mm Hg). All patients underwent ultrasound examination of the kidneys, intrarenal hemodynamic parameters - Doppler indices PI, RI, Vmax, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), microalbuminuria, as well as a general clinical examination and laboratory tests.

Results. According to our study, in Group I, 68% of patients with type 2 diabetes already in the normoalbuminuric stage of the disease have functional renal impairment. In patients with type 2 diabetes in the normoalbuminuric stage of DN development, hyperfiltration is observed in 62% of cases, renomegaly in 74% of cases, vasodilation type of intrarenal hemodynamics in 58% of cases, and endothelial dysfunction in 44% of cases. In Group II, in patients with DN caused by type 2 diabetes in the MAU stage, hyperfiltration is observed in 52% of cases, renomegaly in 69% of cases, vasospastic type of intrarenal hemodynamics in 61.5% of cases, and endothelial dysfunction in 57.8% of cases. In hypertensive patients with DN caused by type 2 diabetes, in

the MAU stage, a decrease in the filtration level was observed in 37.5% of cases, renomegaly in 72.5% of cases, vasospastic type of intrarenal hemodynamics in 78.4% of cases, and endothelial dysfunction in 75.6% of cases.

Conclusions. Thus, ultrasound examination of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and DN reveals changes in renal hemodynamics. With an increase in the duration of the underlying disease, pathology of the vascular wall of the larger trunk renal arteries occurs. Ultrasound examination of renal hemodynamics in patients with DN reveals changes in velocity indicators earlier, while a decrease in the indices of peripheral resistance PI and RI is more typical for patients suffering from diabetes mellitus for more than 5-10 years. Ultrasound with color Doppler blood flow can be used in a complex of clinical examination of patients with DN for early detection of kidney damage

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